

System identification and control of the ankle joint with functional electrical stimulation

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Abstract: The control of the ankle joint induced by functional electrical stimulation (FES) is especially for paraplegic patients of high interest as it allows to partly re-gain the functionality of the lower limb. For this reason, we developed a Simulink model of the ankle joint which describes the dynamic behavior regarding the activation and force development of the three muscle groups of the lower leg. System identification showed that the muscle's behaviour is highly non linear and strongly differs with the condition of the subject. The overall system behavior (black box modelling) was identified via tests on individual subjects on a mechanical test bench. Two control approaches, a PID and an iterative learning controller (ILC), were designed and evaluated.

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I. Introduction

People suffering from paralysis due to a stroke or spinal cord injury (SCI) often face severe movement restrictions. The disconnection between the first and second motor neuron blocks the pathway of the physiological action potentials and causes the loss of volitional muscle contraction. A therapy regarding the limbs can be provided either by pure external and passive motion through a physiotherapist or an exoskeleton or by artificial stimulation of neurons through electrodes. The latter method is named functional electrical stimulation (FES) and can be classified as a motoric neuroprosthesis. However, the muscle response is way more uncertain, unpredictable and less precise than the physiological one such that a FES controller is needed. In this work, the FES device RehaMove3 (Hasomed, Magdeburg, Germany) was used to control the ankle joint. For this purpose, we performed black-box model testing on a mechanical test bench to identify the system's dynamic of the three main muscle groups. We also present two design approaches for the FES using PID and iterative learning control (ILC).

II. Material and methods

White-box model

The model describes the FES induced muscle contraction and the overall torque of the ankle joint which is dependent on the stimulating impulse parameters (pulsewidth, current amplitude and frequency), as well as individual subject conditions (muscle fatigue, muscle length, and shortening velocity). Summarizing active and passive torques as elasticity and viscosity gives the resulting torque of the joint which then leads to the angle acceleration by considering the ankle's inertia. The theoretical muscle modelling closely follows the results provided by Riener and Fuhr [1] focusing on three shank muscles (M. soleus, M. gastrocnemius and M. tibialis anterior). The model is further used to simulate the performance of the ILC and to test the working principle.

Black-box system identification

A mechanical test bench (see Fig. 1) is used to examine the non-linear spatial muscle activation for a constant frequency (30 Hz) and current amplitudes (10-40 mA). The subject's shank is fixed and the isometric muscle response is measured by a differential torque sensor (Lorenz DR-2477-P). Fig. 3 shows the resulting torque-pulsewidth relation which is approximately linear between the activation threshold and saturation.

Fig. 1: Test bench with foot plate (1) and torque sensor (3) for system identification (left), experimental setup (right).

Control design

Fig. 2: Experimental setup with angle encoder and FES electrodes.

The application of closed-loop control is enabled by using an angle encoder (see Fig. 2) attached to a foot plate and an aluminium profile parallel to the shank. A Simulink block [2] implementing a first order P-ILC [3] is modified and applied with a step-time of 0.1 s and a learning rate γ between 0.005 and 0.01. The time interval Δt_i between error estimation and output adjustment is set by recording the response to three FES impulses (triplet). The PID gains for both dorsal- and plantarflexors are tuned following one method of Ziegler-Nichols [4] which is based on the analysis of a step-response. The PID outputs are then aligned by introducing the threshold PID_{thres} from which all higher outputs are shifted to

the linear activation range which results in avoiding the lower dead control space. Furthermore, the control output is limited by the estimated saturation.

III. Results and discussion

All trials were conducted using bi-polar rectangular impulses with a constant frequency of 30 Hz and the ankle was freely movable without ground contact. Fig. 3 shows the application of the ILC. The RMSE of the angle is reduced over the iterations but occurring overshoots due to reflex twitches can hardly be compensated.

Fig. 3: ILC trial with $\Delta t_i = 0.4$ s and $\gamma = 0.01$.

The results of the test bench shown in Fig. 4 allow to identify the activation threshold and saturation which are then used to optimize the PID control. An offset corresponding to the influence of gravity is subtracted and the measurements are median filtered for evaluation. The PID control shown in Fig. 5 yields a better performance regarding the overall and maximum RMSE in comparison to the ILC. The minimum RMSE per period of 1.57° is however comparable to the ILC trial (1.51°).

Fig. 4: System response of the dorsalflexors to an impulse train with rising pulsewidth and constant current amplitude (25 mA) and frequency (30 Hz).

Fig. 5: PID with aligned control output.

IV. Conclusions

Both control approaches provided the basic functionality for periodic movements using pulsewidth modulation with current amplitude and frequency being constant. The ILC-experiments showed that the choice of the learning rate γ and the learning time interval Δt_i is crucial and that the controller is vulnerable to distortions as these affect upcoming periods. The identification of the linear range of muscle activation contributed to a more precise PID control as dead control spaces were avoided. The minimum RMSE per period of the ILC was comparable to the PID control even though the system was modelled as a black-box. The overall and maximum RMSE were however higher in the case of using the ILC. Only healthy volunteers were involved so further experiments with paralyzed subjects are necessary if rehabilitation purposes are desired.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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